

ARE CLASSIFIERS DEFINITE MARKERS OF PLURALITY IN JAPANESE?

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The purpose of this paper is to discuss whether classifiers in Japanese behave like markers of definiteness or not. It is well known that Japanese is an articleless language. Such an explanation turns out to be useful, since demonstratives together with the category of classifiers and number represent the principal means of individuation not only in Japanese, but in most languages.

Keywords: Classifiers, Japanese, Number, Plurality, Definiteness, Countability, Noun Phrases.

Classifiers are sensitive to the semantic properties of the noun such as countability. The problem of countability in Japanese is not restricted only to classifiers, but subsumes a larger array of expressions. Nouns like *douryou* (power), *mizu* (water) or *jiyuu* (freedom) are described as uncountable. Uncountable nouns show pluralities of individuals which are not alike and usually denote ideas, abstract nouns or unbounded mass while nouns like *gakusei* (student), *juuyaku* (director) etc. can be counted and show pluralities of individuals which are alike. Since Japanese does not have a plural morpheme, the difference between countability and uncountability is expressed by employing different classifiers:

- | | |
|------------------------|-----------------------|
| (1) a. juu mai no kami | - ten pieces of paper |
| b. juu en (okane) | - ten yens (money) |
| c. juu kagetsu | - ten months |
| d. juu gatsu | - October |

Unlike English, classifiers in Japanese are a necessary part of the category of Number and they render the Noun Phrase valid. There is a striking difference since in English classifiers are usually employed to make a difference between countable/uncountable nouns, with mass nouns being the most prominent representative of such structures.

The examples in (1) are divided in two pairs exhibiting both classifier employment and the free occurrence of numerals based on the ability of nouns to denote mass or individuals. As we can notice, examples 1(a) and 1(c) involve the necessary addition of a classifier because the nature of the noun describes a substance that needs to be individualized and, thus it becomes definite: paper and temporal delimitations. Examples in 1(b) and 1(d), on the opposite, are instances of a mass that cannot be divided and are devoid of the necessity to employ classifiers: money (*okane*) is semantically emphasized as kinds, while the temporal unit of a month is understood as a proper noun. Charles (1988) dedicates a few dozen paragraphs to the substitution of proper nouns into numerals and argues that the difference between 1(c) and 1(d) proves that Japanese makes a distinction in terms of cardinal and ordinal numerals, which must be syntactically justified since it is marked by the occurrence of a classifier at deep structure and renders a definite interpretation.

The semantic structure of classifiers in Japanese encompasses all kinds of entities, from inanimate to animate, from distinct shapes to colors, from animals to humans, from buildings to landforms. Kuno (1973) metaphorically characterizes this aspect of Japanese as a suite of features that resemble the behavior of a chameleon with everchanging nuances. Plurality of nouns in Japanese is not syntactically marked and a noun can both be singular and plural in many contexts without the necessity of numeral employment (Shibatani, 2005:42). Borer (2005) establishes that plural markers and classifiers are in syntactic complementary distribution, realizing the same head, namely Div, building on the facts that a plural marker and a classifier distributionally appear together, and that they share the same function of individuation. The same applies for Japanese (Kuno, 1973:58)

- | | |
|--------------------------------|---|
| 2. a. nijuu nin no gakusei | - twenty students |
| b. takusan no gakusei | - a lot of students |
| c. nipon no mizu | - two bottles of water |
| d. chiizu no mitsutsu no bubun | - two parts of cheese |
| e. chikara ga tsuyoi | - much power (lit. power is big) |
| f. ouku/subete no chisei | - much intelligence (lit. many intelligences) |
| g. yuushuu na chisei | - much intelligence (lit. excellent intelligence) |

Some authors like Shigeko (1991) suggest that in Japanese the plural marker and a classifier can co-occur, and that the plural does not instantiate the same functional head that a classifier realizes.

This conclusion suggests that plurals and classifiers are not in syntactic complementary distribution in these classifier languages and she proposes examples like 2(e) and 2(g) where the plurality of abstract nouns such as *intelligence* is marked through the employment of adjectives in order to have a clearly defined plural. The exception in 2(f) is only argued in favor of by Yamada (1997), who claims to have encountered it in a particular work by Shibatani. Nonetheless, such a structure is criticized by most Japanese linguists (see Shibatani, 2009).

One feature that distinguishes between countable and uncountable nouns in Japanese is that uncountable nouns cannot be pluralized by means of quantifiers (*takusan*, *sukoshi* etc), something that is visible in examples 2(a)-2(c). Shibatani (2009) provides a notable case of plurality in Japanese by bringing into discussion the example in 2(d) where the mass noun *cheese* is through

the employment of a numeral and a common noun „part”. The salient characteristic of this phenomenon is that the numeral becomes nominalized through „no

Another argument brought by Takezawa (2016) in favor of the definite nature of classifiers in Japanese is that no classifier can occur outside a predicative or nominal structure. Downing (2005) illustrates this idea by placing the NC in several contexts and creating minimal triplets. First, the data in (2) contain an intensional predicate, *sagasu* 'look for'. (2a), with the pre-nominal NC, is ambiguous between specific and non-specific readings; there might be particular nurses that the hospital is looking for, or the hospital is looking for any three nurses. The floating NC construction in (2b) strongly favors the non-specific reading. Finally, and crucially, the post-nominal NC in (2c) is ungrammatical:

- (3) a. *Ano byooiin-ga san-nin-no kangohu-o sagasi-teiru (koto)*
that hospital-Nom three-CL no nurse-Acc looking for-Asp fact
'(the fact that) that hospital is looking for three nurses'
(specific, non-specific)

- b. *Ano byooiin-ga kangohu-o san-nin sagashi-teiru (koto)*
that hospital-Nom nurse-Acc three-CL looking for-Prog fact
'(the fact that) that hospital is looking for three nurses'
(*specific, non-specific)

- c. *Ano byooiin-ga kangohu san-nin-o sagasi-teiru (koto)*
that hospital-Nom nurse three-CL-Acc looking for-Asp fact
'(the fact that) that hospital is looking for three nurses'
(specific, *non-specific)

Numeral classifiers are organized into a grammatical system that reflects how speakers categorize objects that they count or quantify.

Classifiers usually occur adjacent to quantity expressions including numbers. The selection of numeral classifiers is determined by the inherent semantic features of the noun being quantified or counted (Watanabe, 2006:42). These properties are illustrated below:(4)

Tsujimura (2007), following Shibatani (2004), proposes a number of syntactic and semantic properties that characterize Japanese in terms of countability. As a matter of fact, it results that Nominals in classifier languages like Japanese have the following properties:

a. Countability cannot be expressed independently through the employment of numerals alone, but they must be adjoined to a highly specified classifier which, together with the numeral, form a Nominal Phrase, meaning that it behaves like a nominal adjective:

(5) *ichi-*(rin)-no hana*

Num.One, CLASS, GEN., N.Flower

„One Flower”

b. There are no plurality markers on nouns, with a few exceptions like *-tachi*, or *-gata*, which act like suffixes and are lexical in nature (e.g. the same noun as (3) is used in the following examples below). Moreover, bare nouns can denote kinds (Krifka 1995):

(6) *go-rin-no hana*

Num.Five, CLASS., GEN., N.

Flower

‘Five flowers’

(7) *takusan-no hana*

Adv.Many,

GEN., N.Flower

‘A lot of flowers’

The denotations of nouns in obligatory classifier languages are incompatible with ‘counting’, and hence incompatible with direct modification by numerals. “The function of classifiers is to turn such denotations into countable ones. Consequently, CL+NP is semantically compatible with a numeral” (Shibatani, 2004:202)

Watanabe (2006) argues that Japanese nouns denoting countable objects have denotations that are semantically compatible with direct modification with counting modifiers, just as their English counterparts. This view is supported by the previous examples, where some numerals occur without classifiers (Shibatani, 2004:2012)

(8) a. *Deeta wa yaku sen no reiyaa ni wakerare...*

N.Data, TOP., Adv.Approximately, Num.One Thousand, N.Layer, Prep.In, V.PRES.Be divided

The data are divided into about 1000 layers...

b. *Chikyuujou ni wa yaku sengohyaku no kasan ga aru.*

N.Earth, Prep.On, TOP., Adv.Approximately, Num.1500, GEN., N.Volcano, NOM., V.PRES.Be

There are approximately 1500 volcanos on Earth.

Classifiers in Japanese form a closed class of linguistic elements and the class cannot be enlarged at will. Naturally, they function as a means of individuation and render definite expressions *per-se*. Countable classifiers cannot be used with uncountable nouns since the latter are expressed by plain numerals:

(9)

a. Tanakasan wa pan o *ikko* katta.

N. Tanaka, COP., N.Bread, ACC., Num.One, CLASS., V.PAST.Buy

Tanaka bought one bread.

b. Tanakasan wa shokupan o *sankin* katta.

N. Tanaka, COP., N.Bread, ACC., N.Three, CLASS., V.PAST.Buy

Tanaka bought three loaves of bread.

Japanese marks the distinction between integral and divided mass nouns through classifiers as well, something that English does not. Example 9(a) makes use of a generic classifier while example 9(b) proposes a highly specified classifier. In these instances, Uehara (1998) proposes that the generic classifier is counting abstract points on a number line (indeed the generic classifier appears to count mass nouns in a manner similar to abstract nouns such as ‘belief’ (Bale et al. 2019)).

10. *Ouku/subete/takasugiru no chisei wa josei ni totte warui koto desu.*

Adv.Too much, GEN., N.Intelligence, COP., N.Woman, DAT., Adj.Very bad, V.Pr.Be

Too much intelligence is detrimental to women.

Example 9(a) and 9(b) are remarkable in that they exhibit the employment of classifiers as both intrinsic and extrinsic quantifiable lexemes in Japanese (Watanabe, 2016:43). More precisely, the first sentence illustrates a common case of classifiers-related structure, where the employment of a quantifier is mandatory in Japanese for all countable nouns, while the latter exhibits a case of uncountable/mass nominal structure individuation, where the classifiers denotes a part of the undifferentiated mass (bread). The difference is syntactically driven due the employment of distinct classifiers with regard to the noun they determine, namely it means that the distinction must be marked in the derivation diagram.

Countability can be expressed in Japanese even without classifiers, especially with numerals that can appear bare in identificational sentences as in 10(a), also with modifiers that do not require classifiers and function as predicates, namely large numbers as in 10(b). A unique characteristic of this property is that bare numerals are usually indicated by the employment of *yaku* (approximately):

(10)

a. Gakkai kaisai ni hitsuyouna gakusei no kazu wa *juugo* da.

N.Conference, DAT., Adj.Necessary, N.Student, GEN., N.Number, Num.Fifteen, V.PRES.Be

The number of students necessary to host a conference is fifteen.

b. Gakkai kaisai ni ikanai gakusei wa *yaku sen-gohyaku* da.

N.Conference, DAT., V.NEG.Go, N.Student, TOP., Adv.Approximately, Num. 1500, V.PRES.Be

The number of students that do not attend the meeting is roughly 1500.

Yamada (1997) links this phenomenon to a common A' -movement, where numerals and classifiers can front to preverbal positions. This again supports the fact that the numeral and classifier in Japanese are definite and result in a constituent, regardless of their morpho-phonological properties—if it were a (fused) head it would not be able to undergo phrasal movement. The idea is that „higher numbers are able to complete the structure of a NP on a self-supporting mapping between numerosity and objectivity” (pp.21). He further argues in favor of a structure that includes both lower and higher numerals in copulative contexts, where classifiers are omitted:

11. Tanakasan wa *ringo nana to kome hyaku* o tabemashita.

N.Tanaka, COP., N.Apple, Num.Seven, Prep., N.Rice, Num.Hundred, ACC., V.PAST. Eat

Tanaka ate seven apples and one hundred grains of rice.

His proposal is not supported by linguists, since the occurrence of such an example is quite rare. Moreover, according to Tsujimura (2007), whatever type-shifting takes place to go from modifier numerals to counting would work slightly differently with respect to the semantic contribution of the classifier. More precisely, the syntactic structure of classifiers cannot allow co-indexation of heterogeneous numerals without the intricate specification of numeral properties peculiar to each case, namely for lower and higher numerals.

Countability in Japanese is not restricted to numerals and classifiers alone, but it is also rendered through the employment of a limited number of nominal constructions that bear plural or singular interpretation like, for example, *tasuu* (many), *shousuu* (few). These are analyzed by Shibatani as nouns, but function as classifiers (Shibatani, 2004:213)

(12) Kinoo-no jiko-de-wa *tasuu-no* sisha-ga deta yooda.

Adv.Yesterday-GEN,N.Accident-TOP,Adv.Many-GEN,N.fatality-NOM,V.PAST.Come out,EVID

‘It seems that the accident yesterday resulted in many fatalities.’

Shoosuu-no yuufukuna hito-nomi-ga yuuguusareteiru.

Noun.Few-GEN,Adj.Wealthy,N.Person,Prep.Only,NOM.N.PAST/PASS.Treat

‘Only a few wealthy people are treated well.’

These specific adverbs exhibit peculiar morphological properties that ellude the necessity of

employing classifiers as discussed by Takezawa (2016:14) and can only occur in a nominal context introduced by a nominal particle. This behavior owns its nature to the following factors: both *tasuu* and *shousuu* are compound nouns formed by kanji that pertain to lexemes corresponding to their English counterparts *many*, respectively *little* and *number*. Even though they are adverbs at origin, the sentential use of *tasuu* and *shosuu* render them as nouns (Shibatani, 2005:488). 13 is ungrammatical, as discussed by Takezawa (2016:15):

13.* Kare no kotoba wa *shousuu* datta ga, kare no kōdō wa *tasuu* deshita.

Pr.He, GEN, N.Word, COP., N.Few, V.PAST. Be, Pr.He, GEN., N.Action, COP., N.Many, V.PAST.Be

Even though his words were scarce, his actions were many.

Some other constructions peculiar to Japanese (*nanbyaku to iuu* - hundreds, *nanzen to iuu* - thousands) also do not require classifiers. Nonetheless, this is due to the fact that such constructions are predicative in nature and would draw attention to the previous examples, where we showed that some numerals are independent in predicative contexts:

14. Sono tookoo-ni nan-byaku-toiuu komento-ga tsuita.

Pron.Dem.That,N.Post,Prep.To,Num.One Hundred,N.Comment-NOM,V.PAST.Provide

‘That post got hundreds of comments.’

(Shibatani, 2004:214)

According to Watanabe (2006), the constructions in 12 are syntactically determined and form a distinctive class of countability markers, since their occurrence is context sensitive and implies that the nouns they determine are countable in nature (Watanabe, 2006:31)

15. a.# Taro-wa *tasuu-no ase-o* kaita.

Taro-TOP many-GEN sweat-ACC secreted (intended)

‘Taro sweated a lot.’

b.# Taro-wa *nan-byaku-toiuu ase-o* kaita.

Taro-TOP what-100-say sweat-ACC secreted (intended)

‘Taro sweated a lot.’

(Watanabe, 2006:35)

The contrast here shows that the measure expression in a classifier position is specifying a measure function that is compatible with a non-atomic predicate. Japanese classifiers, which already have a measure function built in, must necessarily combine with an atomic noun (Shibatani, 2005:88). This built-in measure function would essentially require an object proportionally equivalent to the meaning of the generic classifier it is assigned to. For this reason, Watanabe (2006:36) assumes that *tasuu* and *nanbyaku to iuu* function to create an atomic predicate, which ultimately

bans the occurrence with noun *ase* since there are no numerals to combine with atomic nouns.

(16) a. *Taro-wa *subete-no gyooza 100-ko-o* tabe-ta.

(∀-no NNC) Taro-Top ∀-Gen dumpling100-CL-Acc eat-Past*

b. Taro-wa *100-ko-no gyooza subete-o* tabe-ta.

(NC-no N ∀) Taro-Top 100-CL-Gen dumpling ∀-Acc eat-Past

‘Taro ate all of the 100 dumplings.’

(Tsujimura, 2007:52)

It is assumed with a long line of research (see Murasugi 1991, Kawashima 1998, Watanabe 2006 among many others) that the post-nominal element in Japanese is a head selecting what is on its left as the complement. This makes sense as Japanese is known to be a strict head-final language, disallowing any expression other than some quantity expressions (in particular, the NCs) to appear following the noun (Shibatani, 2005:148)

Conclusion:

The purpose of this paper was to demonstrate that classifiers in Japanese, an articleless language, behave like markers of definiteness in the absence of other means of numeral individuation. It is well known that Japanese is an articleless language. Such an explanation turns out to be useful, since demonstratives together with the category of classifiers and number represent the main methods of illustrating uniqueness not only in Japanese, but in most languages. One of the arguments we employed was that classifiers in Japanese form a closed class of fixed linguistic elements which cannot be expanded at will. Naturally, they must be indicated to function as a means of individuation and render definite expressions *per-se*. One observation we noticed was that there is an instance where countable classifiers cannot be used with uncountable nouns since the latter are expressed by plain numerals as in example (9).

One reliable characteristic which transform a certain element into a linguistic bearer of definiteness is that it must occur in a nominal structure. I showed that in Japanese there is classifier that occurs outside a predicative or nominal structure. Downing (2005) illustrates this idea by placing the NC in several contexts and creating minimal triplets. The category of Number cannot be expressed independently as in English through the employment of numerals alone, but the existence of a highly specified classifier is mandatory, to form a Nominal Phrase together with the numeral, so one can assume that it must behave like a nominal adjective. There are no plurality markers on nouns, with a few exceptions like *-tachi*, or *-gata*, which act like suffixes and are lexical in nature, but they can also be used to indicate familiarity or in reiterative contexts, so one cannot bring into discussion a syntactic background. Moreover, as showed by Krifka (1995) bare nouns can denote kinds.

The problem of countability in Japanese is not restricted only to classifiers, but subsumes a larger array of expressions. Nouns like *douryou* (power), *mizu* (water) or *jiyuu* (freedom) are described as uncountable.

Uncountable nouns show pluralities of individuals which are not alike and usually denote ideas, abstract nouns or unbounded mass while nouns like *gakusei* (student), *juuyaku* (director) etc. can be counted and show pluralities of individuals which are alike. Since Japanese does not have a plural morpheme, we endeavored to emphasize that the difference between countability and uncountability is expressed by employing different classifiers. As such, classifiers in Japanese must be understood as markers of definiteness, and they bestow definite interpretation to the lexemes in a Nominal Phrase in the same manner as articles do in English.

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